

THE EFFECT OF CORE-SHELL NANOPARTICLES ON STRENGTHENING AND TOUGHENING OF POLYLACTIDE AND JUTE FIBER REINFORCED POLYLACTIDE COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The strengthening and toughening of polylactide (PLA) and natural fiber reinforced PLA composite has been a challenge of green composite development for many years. In this paper, a designed core-shell nanoparticles were incorporated to achieve the simultaneous enhancement of strength and toughness of PLA and jute fiber/PLA composite. The core-shell nanoparticle was synthesized via grafting polymerization, in which the inner core and outer shell were rigid and rubbery phase, respectively. The effect of core-shell nanoparticle on thermal and mechanical properties of both PLA resin and jute fiber/PLA composite were measured. As the results presented, the thermal stability of jute fiber/PLA composite improved due to incorporating the core-shell nanoparticle. Furthermore, the glass transition temperature and melting temperature of PLA resin and jute fiber/PLA composite maintained the constant. More attractively, the mechanical testing results showed that the addition of core-shell nanoparticle contributes to the simultaneous improvement of the stiffness, strength, elongation at break and toughness of both PLA resin and jute fiber/PLA composite. Causally, the synergetic effect between rigid core and ductile shell and strong filler/matrix interfacial interaction play a significant effect on this remarkable increment of mechanical properties. The fracture surface morphology of PLA/core-shell nanocomposite obtained by the field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) suggested that the micro-cracks, shear band and fibrillation of the matrix induced by the core-shell filler are the main causes of toughness improvement.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the natural fiber composite (NFC) has been applied in automotive industry, building construction and sports accessories due to its advantages compared to the synthetic fiber composite, such as environment-friendliness, sustainability, low cost, light weight and high specific strength and stiffness [1]. For further to achieve the full biodegradability and reduce petroleum consumption, using the biodegradable polymers as the matrix of the NFC is an excellent choice. Polylactide, which is produced from renewable agricultural raw materials is the most promising biodegradable polymer due to its high strength, stiffness, transparency and commercial production [2]. Therefore, many investigations have been conducted on natural fiber reinforced polylactide composite [3-5], while the inferior mechanical properties of these NFPC limit their more extensive industrial applications. So some strategies have been developed, for instance, improving the interfacial adhesion between natural fiber and PLA matrix [6,7]. Huda et al. [8] used the alkali, silane and alkali followed by silane to treat the kenaf fiber, respectively. They found that the alkali followed by silane treated fiber

reinforced composite showed more superior flexural strength and storage modulus due to the improved interfacial compatibility between the hydrophilic natural fiber and hydrophobic PLA matrix. Except for the fiber surface treatment, the processing condition has also been ameliorated to enhance the performance of NFPC [9]. For example, Plackett et al. [10] investigated the effect of heating temperature and time of compression molding on performances of NFPC. They concluded that the tensile strength of NFPC prepared at 210 °C (3min) increased 38% compared to that of NFPC prepared at 180 °C (10 min) resulting from the adequate impregnation.

In addition to the optimization of interfacial adhesion and processing condition, the modification of matrix is also an efficient strategy to improve the properties of NFPC. However, there are only a few publications in this regard. Kumar et al. [11] added the montmorillonite clay into PLA matrix to investigate its effect on flax fabric reinforced composite. The results showed that the Young's modulus of the hybrid NFPC increased remarkably, but its tensile strength increased slightly or even decreased, and the elongation at break declined seriously. This may be attributed to the weakened interfacial adhesion of modifier/matrix and the higher stiffness of montmorillonite clay compared to the PLA resin. More recently, Thitsartarn et al. [12] designed molecularly a promising core-shell nanoparticle to modify the epoxy resin. The filler was consisted of rigid core and rubbery shell, which provides the reinforcement and flexibility to the epoxy nanocomposite, respectively. The active functional groups on outer shell make the filler strongly bound to the matrix. Besides, the rigid and rubbery segments were connected via covalent linkages and hence avoided the phase separation. As a result, the incorporation of this core-shell modifier improved the strength and toughness of epoxy simultaneously. Nevertheless, this excellent modifier has not been applied to enhance the performance of NFPC.

In this paper, a kind of rigid-flexible core-shell nanoparticle was introduced into the PLA matrix to improve the mechanical properties of woven jute fiber reinforced PLA composite. The nano-silica and poly (butyl acrylate) were designed as the rigid inner core and rubbery outer shell of core-shell filler, respectively. The effect of core-shell nanoparticle on crystalline and thermal properties of NFPC were investigated by the X-ray diffraction (WAXD), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Furthermore, the contribution of core-shell nanofiller to the strength, stiffness and ductility of NFPC were also explored by the tensile and flexural tests. Subsequently, the mechanism of mechanical enhancement and synergistic effect of designed core-shell nanoparticle were also analyzed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The AGET ATRP (activators generated by electron transfer, atom-transfer radical polymerization) was utilized to synthesize the silica-rubber core-shell nanoparticle [13, 14]. As shown in Fig. 1, the amino-functionalized silica nanoparticles ($\text{SiO}_2\text{-NH}_2$) was first prepared by the silanization reaction of abundant hydroxyl on the silica surface with silane coupling agent (APTES) for 16 h at 95 °C in an oil bath. Subsequently, to realize the polymerization grafting of butyl acrylate (BA) monomer, the initiator was immobilized at the surface of silanized silica to obtain the $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Br}$. The 2-bromoisobutyryl bromide (BiB) was added dropwise to mixed solution of silanized silica, trimethylamine and toluene. The immobilization reaction was processed for 3 h at 0 °C and 12 h at room temperature. Then the iron-mediated AGET ATRP technique was applied to synthesize the $\text{SiO}_2\text{-PBA}$ core-shell nanoparticle. In the presence of initiator, graft polymerization of the butyl acrylate (BA) rubber shell was initiated on the nano-silica surface using the FeCl_3 /triphenylphosphine (PPh_3) as catalyst complex and ascorbic acid (VC) as reducing agent. The polymerization procedure was carried on for 8 h at 90 °C. The obtained rigid core-soft shell nanoparticle with end bromine group was denoted as $\text{SiO}_2\text{-PBA-Br}$. Furthermore, to promote the covalent bonding between core-shell filler and polylactide matrix, the 'click' reaction

was used to transfer the end bromine group of PBA shell to the active amine group. The SiO₂-PBA-Br core-shell particle, trimethylamine and cysteamine were dissolved in tetrahydrofuran and stirred overnight at room temperature. The obtained core-shell nanoparticle with the terminal amino group was designated as SiO₂-PBA-NH₂.

Fig 1: Synthesis schematic of silica-rubber core-shell nanoparticle

To improve the interfacial adhesion between hydrophilic jute fiber and hydrophobic PLA, the surface treatment of natural jute fiber was implemented firstly. The jute fibers were immersed in sodium hydroxide solution (5% w/v) for 2 h at room temperature and then were washed with distilled water until pH of 7. After washing, the fibers were dried in air for 12 h followed by dried in vacuum oven at 80 °C for 6h. The alkali treated fibers were immersed in the mixture of water/ethanol (40:60 w/w) with 5 wt.% APTES (weight percentage compared to the fiber) for 3 h. Then the fibers were washed and dried in air for 12 h followed by dried in vacuum oven at 80 °C for 6h.

The composite laminates containing 40 wt.% woven jute fiber were fabricated by hot pressing of prepregs, as shown in Fig. 2. Firstly, the specific weight of dried PLA pellet was dissolved in the dichloromethane. The 1 wt.% core-shell nanoparticle (SiO₂-PBA-NH₂) was dispersed in ethanol and sonicated for 30 min. Then, the nanoparticle solution was mixed with the PLA resin and the mixture was stirred to homogeneity. The obtained modified matrix was poured onto the woven jute fiber to prepare the prepregs. After the solvent volatilizing, the obtained prepregs were dried in the vacuum at 60 °C. Finally, the PLA/jute fiber prepregs were stacked in the mold and hot pressed at 160 °C for 20 min. The obtained sample is denoted as NFPC/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂. The NFPC represents the jute fiber reinforced unmodified-PLA composite. For comparison, the nanoparticles of SiO₂ and SiO₂-NH₂ were also used to modify the PLA matrix, the as-prepared jute fiber reinforced nanocomposites are designated as NFPC/SiO₂ and NFPC/SiO₂-NH₂.

Fig.2: Fabrication of jute reinforced PLA laminated composite

The tensile properties of fiber reinforced laminate were obtained according to the ASTM Standard D3039 using an Instron 5500R testing machine at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. The flexural properties were measured according to ASTM D790 using Zwick/Roell Z010 machine. The fracture surface morphologies of the tensile samples were observed using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JEOL JSM 6390). Dispersion of core-shell nanoparticles in PLA matrix and detailed fracture morphology of PLA/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ nanocomposite were examined using the field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, ZEISS, 15 kV).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mechanical properties of the core-shell filler modified PLA nanocomposite were evaluated via the tensile, flexural and impact tests. The toughness was calculated by integrating the tensile stress–strain curves. The brittle fracture behaviors of tensile and flexural of neat PLA and PLA nanocomposite can be observed from the stress–strain curves shown in Fig. 3. It is reported that the stress whitening and crazing formed in the slow cooling samples after hot pressing resulted in a brittle fracture. From Fig. 3, the tensile strength of neat PLA is 43.1 MPa, with the incorporation of 1wt% SiO₂-NH₂ and SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ nanoparticle, the tensile strength of nanocomposite is enhanced 17.6% and 36.9%, which is much higher than the PLA/SiO₂ of 4.2%. This could be attributed to the effective stress transfer between nanofillers and PLA matrix resulting from the perfect interfacial interactions that the amidogen on the silica surface can be chemically bond to the carboxyl of PLA.

Fig. 3: The effect of core-shell on the mechanical properties of PLA (a) Tensile stress-strain curves (b) The tensile, flexural and impact properties of neat PLA and core-shell/PLA nanocomposite

It can be seen that the flexural properties of PLA and PLA nanocomposite are more superior to their tensile properties. The flexural strength and modulus of neat PLA are 63.3 MPa and 2.42 GPa, respectively. The addition of raw SiO₂ increased slightly the flexural strength to 71.2 MPa and reduced the flexural modulus to 2.28 GPa. The minute quantity of raw SiO₂ (1 wt%) has less enhancement on mechanical properties of polymer matrix. However, the SiO₂-NH₂ nanoparticle modified by the APTES coupling agent can moderately improve the flexural strength by 18.5% and the modulus was nearly no reduced, which due to the presence of terminated amine group on the surface of silica particles, the SiO₂-NH₂ nanoparticle can be comparatively well dispersed in the matrix to enhance the mechanical properties of the composites. Moreover, the incorporation of SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ core-shell nanoparticle significantly increased the flexural strength and modulus by 61.8% and 33.9% compared to the neat PLA. The chemical bonding between particle and matrix via amidation reaction of amino group on core-

shell surface and carboxyl functionality of PLA can decrease the debonding of particles and promote the load transfer.

In addition to the enhancement of tensile and flexural strength, the silica-rubber core-shell nanoparticle exhibits a remarkable toughening effect on PLA. With the incorporation of SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ nanoparticles, the toughness and elongation at break of PLA nanocomposite are improved 80.4% and 29.5%, respectively, compared with neat PLA, which has a distinct advantage over the nanocomposite modified by the other fillers used in this paper. This may result from the good interfacial adhesion and the crack tip pinning effect. Meanwhile, the rubber layer of core-shell particle can initiate the crazes that can dissipate the energy effectively. Besides, from the Fig. 3 (b), the impact strength of PLA/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ nanocomposite is improved to 15.85 kJ m⁻² from 13.88 kJ m⁻², an increment of 14.2% with only 1wt% loading of nanofiller. The other rigid nanoparticles have nearly no enhancement on the impact resistance of PLA. It is expressly indicated that the insertion of PBA rubber layer with excellent ductility can absorb more impact energy. Meanwhile, the good interfacial interaction between the modified nanofiller and matrix can hinder the propagation of crack to reinforce the impact resistance.

The results of most researches revealed that the elongation at break of PLA composite was enhanced at the expense of the obviously decline of their strength and stiffness. This has demonstrated the advantage of our formulation that only a low loading of core-shell nanoparticles can achieve the balance of strengthening and toughening resulting from the synergistic effect between rigid core and rubber shell.

To illustrate the toughening mechanism, the fracture surface morphologies of core-shell reinforced PLA matrix nanocomposite after tensile tests are shown in Fig. 4. The 1 wt.% of SiO₂-PBA core-shell nanoparticles are homogeneously distributed in the PLA matrix (labelled by yellow circles in Fig. 4 (a)). The less cavitation/voids occurs in the fracture surface, which profits from the desirable interfacial adhesion between core-shell filler and matrix. Being different from the toughening mechanism of pure rubber particle, which the cavitation plays an essential role, the core-shell particle with a superior filler-matrix interaction can also improve the toughness of composite. He et al. [15] concluded that the rubber layer of core-shell particle may initiate the crazes, which is considered to be the key toughening mechanism. Although the crazes didn't appear in our fracture surface, as the red arrows shown in Fig. 4 (a), the flexible rubber layer of core-shell filler facilitates the micro-crack, which is the origin of energy dissipation and thus improves the toughness of nanocomposite. In addition to crack formation, it is hypothesized that the shear band and fibrillation of matrix induced by the core-shell filler also have the significant toughening effect (as labelled by red circles in Fig. 4 (b)). These shear bands occurred near the core-shell particles, which demonstrates that the rigid-flexible filler can induce the inhomogeneous localized plastic deformation of PLA matrix. Moreover, the fibrillation of matrix could absorb energy remarkably to enhance the toughness of composite.

Fig. 4: FE-SEM fracture surface morphologies of PLA/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ nanocomposite. ((b) is the enlargement of corresponding area of (a).)

The tensile and flexural stress-strain curves of neat PLA and nanoparticle modified PLA/jute fiber composites are shown in Fig. 5. It is apparent that all samples showed the brittle fracture behaviors, while the non-linear deformation appeared in the stress-strain curves of PLA/jute fiber composites. The starting of nonlinearity indicated the initial matrix cracking followed by progressive failure of fiber. Moreover, the tensile strength and young's modulus of fiber reinforced composites increased significantly compared to neat PLA, however, their failure strains declined. This can be attributed to the lower failure strain of the jute fiber compared to that of PLA.

Fig. 5: (a) Tensile and (b) Flexural stress-strain curves of neat PLA and PLA/jute fiber composites (NFPC) (SiO₂:Raw nano-silica, SiO₂-NH₂:Silanized nano-silica, SiO₂-PBA-NH₂:Core-shell nanoparticle)

It can be observed that the curve of neat PLA showed a linear evolution, while the PLA/jute fiber composites appeared the initial linear deformation, followed by a non-linear deformation due to the introduction of jute fiber. As shown in Fig. 5 (b), the NFPC exhibits a significant improvement of flexural properties compared to neat PLA, which results from the strong mechanical properties of jute fiber and interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix. Furthermore, the nanoparticles used in modifying the PLA resin had a prominent reinforcement to the NFPC. The effects of raw silica (SiO₂), silanized silica (SiO₂-NH₂) and core-shell nanoparticle (SiO₂-PBA-NH₂) on the flexural strength and modulus of NFPC are shown in Fig. 5 (b). The flexural strength and modulus of NFPC are 87.3 MPa and 4.87 GPa, respectively. In comparison of NFPC, the flexural strength of NFPC/SiO₂-NH₂ composite increased 18.9%. Due to the presence of the terminated amine group on the surface of silica, the SiO₂-NH₂ nanoparticle can be comparatively well dispersed in the matrix to enhance the efficient load transfer between modifier and PLA. Moreover, with incorporation of the SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ core-shell nanofiller, the NFPC/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ composite exhibited the enhanced strength and modulus of 115.3 MPa and 5.33 GPa, respectively, about 32% and 9.4% higher than those of NFPC. The chemical bonding between particle and matrix via amidation reaction of amino group on core-shell surface and carboxyl functionality of PLA can decrease the debonding of particles and promote the load transfer. In addition, the rubber shell of SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ can dissipate effectively local stress to reduce the cavitation of nanoparticles.

To better understand the toughening effect of SiO₂-PBA core-shell nanoparticle on PLA/jute fiber composites, the tensile fracture surfaces of NFPC and NFPC/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ were observed using SEM as shown in Fig. 6. The fracture surface of PLA matrix of NFPC is smooth (Fig. 6 (a)), and some fractured fiber can also be seen. PLA matrix of NFPC/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂ presents a much rougher fracture

surface (Fig. 6 (b)), which demonstrates the localized plastic deformation of PLA matrix can be induced by the core-shell nanoparticle. Fig. 6 (c) and (d) show the fracture morphologies of PLA matrix permeated through jute fiber yarns. It can be seen the fibers were well impregnated at loading of 40 wt.% by PLA resin using the prepreg technology. As presented in Fig. 6 (c), the PLA matrix of NFPC between fiber bundles appears a typical brittle failure. The broken PLA mass disperses surrounding fibers. With incorporation of core-shell nanoparticle, the lamination of matrix between fiber bundles occurs, exhibiting a more ductile fracture (Fig. 6 (d)). Excepting for the fibrillation effect induced by the core-shell filler, the shear yielding produced at the interface between fiber bundles and matrix also contributes to the exfoliation of PLA.

Fig. 6: SEM fracture surface morphologies of PLA/jute fibre composites (a and c) NFPC (b and d) NFPC/SiO₂-PBA-NH₂.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The modification of PLA matrix by incorporating the rigid-soft core-shell nanoparticle has been as a strategy to improve the mechanical properties of woven jute fiber reinforced PLA laminated composite. The core-shell nanoparticle with both the rigid and rubbery phases was synthesized via chemical polymerization of nano-silica as the inner core and poly (butyl acrylate) as outer shell. The tensile and flexural tests results showed that with the core-shell nanofiller adding, the strength and stiffness of NFPC were significantly enhanced, especially, the toughness and elongation at break were not impaired. The superior mechanical properties are derived from the strong filler-matrix interactions and efficient synergy of rigid/rubbery phases. Moreover, the fracture surface morphologies of PLA and NFPC revealed that the localized plastic deformation of matrix induced by core-shell filler is the main toughening mechanism.

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